

Impact of Technostress on Student Satisfaction and Student Engagement of University Students in Sri Lanka

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Introduction

The 21st century is typically seen as a technological era and technology has become a vital part of our lives. It was discovered that the utilization of trendy tools, technology, and equipment in higher education increases the student learning engagement and interactions (Ranathunge, 2022). However, while employing technology tools, there are certain additional factors that could be viewed as learning barriers for students, such as, struggle to maintain access to learning platforms, adapt with new digital (Wang, 2020) platforms, mental pressure and stress brought by technological infrastructures (Gonzales, 2018).

Among these technical downsides, Technostress, often known as stress, associated with technology, is increasingly posing a threat to students all over the world (Lazarus, 1966). Technostress, the biggest issue with technology, needs to be lessened to overcome the barriers for student learning (Wang, 2020). Thus, Technostress might be considered a significant issue that may have an impact on Student Satisfaction and Student Engagement. There is, however, still a very few research have been conducted to look at the impact of Technological Stress on Student Satisfaction and Student Engagement, simultaneously. Previous study findings have concluded that further research is required to determine how Technological Stress affects Student Engagement and Student Satisfaction even in the Sri Lankan context (Ranathunge, 2022).

Research Questions

1. What are the factors causing Technostress among undergraduates?
2. What is the effect of those factors on Technostress, Student Satisfaction and Student Engagement?

Methodology

This study used a deductive approach, and it was quantitative in nature. The target population for the study was undergraduates in Sri Lanka, since there was sufficient proof from the literature that Technostress is a common behavior among undergraduates regardless of their context (Aziz, 2021; Ranatunga, 2022). The minimum recommended sample size for the study was calculated as 97 using a sample size calculator developed by Soper (2021). Convenience sampling method was used. Sample selected for the study consisted of undergraduates from both public and private universities representing eight universities in Sri Lanka. The survey questionnaire method was used in this study. All the constructs were measured using already validated items with 7-point Likert scale. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 27.0) software was used to analyze demographic and descriptive data. Due to the complexity of the model and the small sample size, Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) technique was used to analyze the conceptual model (Hair et al., 2016).

According to Kumar (2019), “Conceptual Framework” was the foundation of a study which was built upon the theories related to the research problem. To answer the research questions, a conceptual model was developed based on two popular theories in Technostress literature: Person-Environment Fit Theory (Holland,1970) and Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura,1977). P-E Fit Theory often leads to improved Student Satisfaction, increased Student Engagement with environmental factors (Edwards & Shipp, 2007). Referring to the SCT perspective aligned by Bandura (1977), the author suggested that individuals' attitudes on the use and existence of ICT are not

formed by the circumstances that force them to adopt with technology but also by the results of few relational variables. Those were addressed via the conceptual model. Thus, the conceptual model developed for the current study is shown in Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Results and Discussion

After the data screening, 127 valid responses were used for further analysis. Majority of the respondents were female (58%) and most of the respondents were born between 1997 and 1999 (43%). Most of the respondents were from government universities (57%). The majority of the respondents felt stressed due to increased workload (19%). Reliability and validity measures were established based on the measurement model analysis (Hair et al., 2016). Hypotheses were tested at 95% level of confidence ($p < 0.05$). Five out of ten hypotheses were supported (See Table 1).

Table 1: Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient (β)	T statistics	P values	Outcome
Self-Efficacy -> Student Satisfaction (H1)	0.027	0.255	0.799	Not Supported
Self-Efficacy -> Technostress (H2)	-0.073	0.699	0.485	Not Supported
Student Satisfaction -> Student Engagement (H3)	0.646	6.753	0.000	Supported
Techno Dependency -> Student Satisfaction (H4)	-0.036	0.331	0.740	Not Supported
Techno Dependency -> Technostress (H5)	0.360	3.830	0.000	Supported
Techno Insecurity -> Student Satisfaction (H6)	0.335	2.938	0.003	Supported
Techno Insecurity -> Technostress (H7)	0.036	0.339	0.735	Not Supported
Techno Overload -> Student Satisfaction (H8)	0.371	3.600	0.000	Supported
Techno Overload -> Technostress (H9)	0.521	5.398	0.000	Supported
Technostress -> Student Engagement (H10)	0.161	1.619	0.106	Not Supported

Self-Efficacy did not have a significant effect on Student Satisfaction ($\beta=0.027$, $p=0.799$). The finding contradicted with the previous study by Upadhyaya and Vrinda (2020). Further, Self-Efficacy did not have a significant effect on Technostress ($\beta=-0.073$, $p=0.485$) contradicted with previous research (Attuquayefio & Addo, 2014; Haron et al., 2020). However, Student Satisfaction had a significant effect on Student Engagement ($\beta=0.646$, $p=0.000$) where the finding was consistent with previous research (Christian et al., 2020; Li & Wang, 2020). Techno-Dependency did not have a significant effect on Student Satisfaction ($\beta=-0.036$, $p=0.740$) and contradicted with previous research (Tarafdar, Tu, Ragu-Nathan, & Ragu-Nathan, 2011; Yasin, Ong, & Aziz, 2020). Technology Dependency had a significant positive effect on Technostress ($\beta=0.360$, $p=0.000$) and was consistent with He et al. (2019). There was a significant positive effect of Techno-Insecurity on Student Satisfaction ($\beta=0.335$, $p=0.003$). The finding was consistent with the findings of Komala

and Meena (2017). Further, Techno-Insecurity was not a significant factor influencing Technostress ($\beta = 0.036$, $p = 0.735$). The finding was consistent with Christian et al. (2020). There was a significant positive effect of Techno-Overload on Student Satisfaction ($\beta = 0.371$, $p = 0.000$). This finding contradicted with the findings of Upadhyaya and Vrinda (2020). The findings also revealed that Techno-Overload has a positive effect on Technostress ($\beta = 0.521$, $p = 0.000$). However, findings were not consistent with Christian et al. (2020) and Hsiao et al. (2017). Further, Technostress did not have a significant effect on Student Engagement ($\beta = 0.161$, $p = 0.106$) and was consistent with prior research (Christian et al., 2020; Li & Wang, 2020).

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to identify the factors affecting Technostress, Student Satisfaction and Student Engagement in the Sri Lankan context. To answer the identified research questions, a conceptual model was developed based on two theories in Technostress literature: Person-Environment Fit Theory (Hackman, 1979) and Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1984). The study tried to fill the gap in literature by integrating Person Environment Fit Theory and Social Cognitive Theory to identify the impact of Technostress on Student Satisfaction and Student Engagement. According to the study findings, Technostress had a significant positive effect on Student Satisfaction and Student Engagement. Technology Dependency had a significant positive effect on Technostress. Further, Techno Insecurity and Techno Overload had significant positive effects on Student Satisfaction. Findings further revealed that the effect of Self-Efficacy and Techno Insecurity on Technostress was not significant.

The findings of the study have several practical implications. As the findings indicated a higher impact of Technostress on Student Satisfaction and Student Engagement, universities must arrange and schedule academic work in such a way that students have enough time to finish their assignments while still maintaining a balanced lifestyle. Furthermore, universities can reduce the impact of Technostress by selecting user-friendly instructional technology and providing enough training to students

on how to utilize it. Universities must identify 'at-risk' students and assist them in dealing with Technostress. The current study only studied Technostress generators and did not look at Technostress inhibitors such as technical support, literacy facilitation, and engagement facilitation (Ragu-Nathan et al., 2008). Also, small sample size caused issues in generalizability. In future studies, a larger sample is suggested to further validate the Person Environment Fit Scale and Social Cognitive Theory in this context. Future studies are also encouraged to consider a longitudinal design for studying actual Technostress among university students.

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